

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

EVALUATION OF THE DRAFT COMPETENCE STANDARDS FOR REMOTE-CONTROL VESSEL OPERATORS AND THEIR FUTURE IMPLEMENTATION IN MARITIME EDUCATION

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Abstract

The application and advancement of remote control and autonomous functions in the shipping business has already begun and will increase in the coming years. Remote control functions can be defined as such functions that allow a human operator, while being in a land-based location, to monitor and remotely exercise control over the operations of a given vessel. Currently, there are no IMO instruments that regulate the commercial remote-controlled vessels, nor the technical requirements behind this concept. A safety framework will be necessary to standardize the requirements for unmanned vessels or those with reduced crew. To achieve vessel operation at an equivalent level of safety, remote-control operators must have appropriate competences. However, competence standards for operators have not yet been developed and standardized. The aim of this article is to research and evaluate the progress of various organizations to prepare draft competence standards for supervisors and remote-control operators for maritime and inland navigation and how these standards can be implemented in maritime education. The research methodology employed in this study involved a thorough document analysis of relevant industry reports, guidelines, and documents.

Keywords: remote-controlled vessels; autonomous shipping; unmanned ships; maritime safety framework; competence standards.

Introduction

Shipping plays a major role in maintaining world trade, with over 50 thousand vessels to transport commodities, equating to more than 60 trillion ton-miles internationally (ICS 2022). Skilled and experienced seafarers are an essential part of the stability and safety of shipping. Currently, there are over 1.6 million seafarers worldwide, including 774 thousand officers (ICS 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of seafarers in maintaining the supply chain, while the crew change restrictions caused a significant upset in the shipping industry. The International Maritime Organization (IMO) has recognized the necessity and growing demand of seafarers and encourages governments to treat them as "key workers" who conduct an "essential service" (IMO 2020).

However, human error or the so-called "human factor" remains a critical issue affecting the industry, with over 80% of marine accidents being caused by human-related failures [4]. The psychological strain is one of the crucial factors that invites errors. When the strain becomes too much, decision-making is induced, which causes safety considerations [9]. Excessive psychological burden, also known as "stress," causes fatigue that may affect ship safety significantly (IMO 2019). Ship automation and remote control have emerged as solutions to tackle the problem. The contemporary development of information and communication technology, including computation and artificial intelligence, has inevitably led to the emergence of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS). The shipping industry has seen the development of MASS for several years. For instance, in 2018, Finferries and Rolls-Royce demonstrated an autonomous ship (Rolls-Royce 2018), while a new demonstration project has been initiated by

the Nippon Foundation with the goal of promoting unmanned commercial ships, which are expected to be operational by 2025 (NYK 2020). In addition, Yara International plans to operate a completely unmanned commercial ship in Norway (Maritime Executive 2021).

Although the autonomous capabilities of MASS are extensive, different organizations, such as Lloyd's Register, Maritime UK, and IMO, classify them in various ways. The most advanced level of autonomy, where a ship can operate independently without human supervision, may not be achieved soon because of serious concerns related to safety and security. As the fully autonomous level is unlikely to be addressed in the near future, the remote-control center and remote operator as part of the shore-based infrastructure for ship control will play a vital role in the MASS system [15]. However, international regulatory requirements for RO competence have not been introduced yet, and this presents a challenge.

The implementation of autonomous and remote shipping is expected to cause significant disruptions and challenges in the manning sector, which in turn will require a thorough re-examination of the training frameworks within the maritime industry [1]. Despite the absence of regulatory guidelines, the development of autonomous and remote fleets has not halted, resulting in the emergence of a new profession: the remote operator. The Remote Operator is accountable for ensuring the safe navigation of autonomous vessels from a Remote Operations Center, either through monitoring or direct control. It is possible for deck officers to transition to this new role, but the specific skills and training necessary for this shift have yet to be determined.

The operator, stationed in the shore-based command center, would be responsible for navigating the

ship and supervising the full operational parameters surrounding the everyday vessel tasks. It is generally agreed that the operator must possess specialized skills for the job, although there is currently no clear consensus on what these skills entail or how to train remote-control operators. Two possibilities for the development of this position exist: it could involve the "occupational progression" of a seafarer from a ship-based role to a shore-based position, or the creation of new job opportunities for new hires [12].

The operator should be able to perform the same range of tasks as an equivalent deck officer, if those tasks have not already been automated. With the advent of remote operations, it is natural for seagoing deck officers to become Remote Operators responsible for safe navigation remotely. Any MASS remote-control operator should be able to perform these tasks as efficiently and safely as the current team of deck officers [3].

The primary objective of this article is to investigate the ongoing advancements undertaken by a multitude of organizations with the express purpose of developing and formulating preliminary drafts of competence standards specifically tailored for supervisors and remote-control operators operating in maritime and inland navigation. Additionally, this article seeks to bring forward the complexities surrounding the practical implementation of these standards within the domain of maritime education. In order to accomplish these research objectives, the chosen research methodology employed in this study encompassed an exhaustive document analysis of a wide array of pertinent resources, including industry reports, guidelines, and an extensive collection of documents curated from the shipping industry. Through this systematic approach, the research team aimed to gain insights and a comprehensive understanding of the current state and progress of competence standards development within the dynamic and evolving sphere of remote control and autonomous functions in the shipping industry.

Literature survey

The subject of automation in ships was first addressed by the IMO during the 8th session of the Maritime Safety Committee in March 1964 [7]. As the development and continuous improvement of ship automation have been expanding, the maritime sector is expecting the operation of MASS to be implemented in the near future based on technological advancements. Numerous research projects on MASS have been conducted and are currently ongoing globally, such as the DNV-GL Revolt [17], Kongsberg Maritime Autonomous Shipping, and NYK Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships Trial.

The complex nature of MASS operation and new technologies have presented multiple challenges for the various research projects. In response, the IMO has undertaken a MASS regulatory scoping exercise (RSE) (IMO 2017) aimed at identifying and addressing these issues, while also accommodating technological advancements in the field of MASS (IMO 2018). Another target for the RSE is to assess the impact of autonomy on regulatory frameworks and identify any necessary changes to enable the safe operation of MASSs.

In order to prepare for the future of MASS, deck officers need to be trained in all levels of autonomy, whether they are working on board a vessel or as a remote operator on shore. One solution could be to include these aspects in the STCW competency level courses, as well as providing separate training for officers who plan to transition to the role of remote operator. IMO recognizes that many of its current rules and regulations are not suitable for MASS, as they were developed with conventionally manned ships in mind [12].

In his work, Ramos et al. has provided background on the challenges that operators of MASSs may face, irrespective of their location. Such challenges include information overload, situational awareness, skill degradation, and boredom [14]. On a related note, Nava and Fernanda [13] argued that legal issues regarding liability for collisions must also be considered when developing specific regulations for autonomous and unmanned vessels under the STCW convention, including the UNCLOS, COLREG, and STCW 1978 convention.

Seven skills were identified as very important, in order for the vessel remote-control system to run smoothly: Seamanship, Well-trained and multi-skilled, IT and cyber security literacy, Tool Handling, Communication, Safety awareness, Emergency response [10]. Elaboration of many of these skills is needed to determine the necessary experience and training required to support them. It is evident that both technical and non-technical skills must be integrated into the operator training. Some skills may be acquired through shore-based training by non-seafarers, while others may require practical sea experience, albeit of a shorter duration. Some of the above skills may demand both seafaring experience and training before an operator can assume control of a vessel (IMO 2018).

According to a study on the competency requirements of future seafarers, it is anticipated that some skills will remain essential, but their modified versions will be in higher demand. These skills include critical thinking and quantitative reasoning, technical literacy with a focus on information and communication technology, and environmental sustainability. Additionally, the study highlights the likelihood of the emergence of new knowledge and competencies, such as technological awareness, computing and information skills, learning and self-development, as well as adaptability and flexibility.

In his work, Emad et al. [5] has interviewed key stakeholders in the maritime industry and has concluded that both current and new skills will be needed to operate autonomous ships. Operators should first undergo traditional seafaring training before being upskilled to work with autonomous ships and shore-based stations. In addition, it has been found that the Maritime Education and Training (MET) institutes are currently unprepared to impart the necessary skills and competencies that would be required by future seafarers, primarily because the technology for autonomous ships is still being developed. Therefore, preparations for the future are being impeded due to the uncertainties surrounding technological advancement. Yoshida et al. have proposed a method for establishing regulatory requirements for seafarers' competence based on ship

awareness and can be applied to evaluate regulatory requirements for new MASS [18]. Additionally, the study's results can serve as a foundation for introducing a blend of competence requirements, training for officials, and advanced technology for MASS.

According to Hannaford et al., many deck officers reinforce the belief that shipping companies, unions, and MET facilities are not adequately prepared for the industry's changes. Many survey participants believe that MET will significantly change within the next decade [8]. Another article concludes that the maritime industry needs to reform its education and training methods to prepare seafarers for the future workplace as the shipping industry shifts towards technology-based systems. Additionally, there is a possibility that decentralized education systems will emerge in the industry, including specialized courses and continuous professional development [6]. The survey conducted by Alice et al. resulted in the conclusion that the skills and experience gained at sea are crucial for remote operators, but current training and certification are inadequate for operating autonomous vessels. The current STCW training is not suitable for Industry 4.0, as it lacks skills in cyber security and understanding AI systems [12].

Training needs to evolve to support a more versatile and technical approach and although the Netherlands has combined deck and engineer training courses, this approach might not be sufficient for remote operators or deck officers working with autonomous vessels. To keep up with emerging technologies, training needs to be adaptable and cater to the changing needs of the industry. Nevertheless, the industry is changing rapidly, and the current slow implementation of changes is inadequate. The STCW OOW syllabus must be updated to include training and standards for officers working on autonomous and remote-control vessels, as well as standards for remote-control operators. With the development of MASS fleets in the upcoming years, it is highly likely that conventional vessels will have to interact with MASS. Up to date education and training that encompasses modern vessels and trends will provide opportunities for deck officers interested in exploring the MASS sector.

The first step towards preparing deck officers for the maritime industry's future should be updating the STCW training framework. However, regulatory bodies play a critical role in maintaining international competency standards. Practical onboard training will be critical for remote operators to become familiar with vessels and sailing areas and maintain their skills and experience. Simulation training will also prove useful in preparing remote operators to adapt to a new environment and become comfortable with the user interface. In that regard, type-specific console courses must be established to address the software and potential hardware differences between the remote-control stations of various manufacturers.

Progress in competence standards for remote control operators

DNV, a classification society based in Norway, has introduced in Nov. 2021 the first competence standard for operators of ship remote control centers (RCC) along with a recommended practice for a certification

scheme. This framework aims to establish guidelines for the training, evaluation, and certification of RCC employees who operate or support operations at sea through remote-control facilities. In collaboration with Kongsberg Maritime, Wilhelmsen, the University of South-Eastern Norway, and the Norwegian Maritime Authority, DNV has developed two new standards. The first standard is DNV-RP-0323, which guides the RCC operator examination process and acts as the certification body for granting personnel certificates. It also includes a competence-building process for candidates before taking the RCC operator examination. In addition, the establishment of the foundation for the entire autonomous vessel management procedure and the identification of essential skills are outlined in the DNV SeaSkill standard ST-0324 (DNV 2021).

Kari et al. conducted a study that developed a remote supervisory control prototype for unmanned cargo vessels and invited six participants with sea experience to conduct scenario-based simulation trials as proposed by SCC operators [11]. The study found that using commonly used navigational and collision avoidance technologies in a different way could lead to problems in developing sufficient situation awareness for remote supervisory control tasks. Without adapting the tools to the domain constraints of shore-based remote monitoring and controlling tasks, it was hard for the operators to perform the tasks reliably. Decision-making latencies and automation bias were observed.

In the inland water transport (IWT) sector PLATINA3 Policy Platform has published a Report on competences needed to operate on board systems allowing for automation of inland navigation vessels D3.3. As per the report, the emergence of remotely operated vessels has created a need for new competencies, particularly for nautical inland shipping personnel involved in remote operations. Existing initiatives are advancing from national to cross-border operations, highlighting the need for new competence standards.

Currently, IWT operations are single-vessel based, with remote control from a shore control center and support from an experienced boatman on board who is responsible for regular activities such as maintenance and repair jobs. The need for new competencies in remote vessel operations is urgent, and the current single-vessel-based operational model is not considered economically viable. The D3.3 report proposed a competency framework that includes roles for remote control center operators and supervisors, as well as able boatmen on remote-controlled craft. Proposed standards for professional qualifications on management and operational levels will be considered according to the CESNI framework, with adjustments made based on legislative frameworks and technical requirements. Before developing educational and training programs, it is recommended to accelerate the adoption process in CESNI and to establish required competencies for remote vessel operation qualifications. At present, the European Standard for Qualifications in Inland Navigation has not adopted any standards for remote control operators.

It is evident that the advancement of automation technology calls for the establishment of competency

standards for operators who would be operating and supervising remote control systems. Thus, it is essential to create and implement these standards in parallel with the rise of autonomous technology to ensure safe and efficient operations.

The development of standards for remote control operators is still in its infancy, with only DNV making significant progress. However, the maritime and inland waterway transport industries are waiting for remote control vessels to become more actively involved in global trade before they begin to seriously contemplate the necessity for the establishment of standards and guidelines in this field. Until then, it is likely that the current minimal levels of regulation and guidance will remain in place.

Considering the ongoing developments in remote control vessel technology, it is probable that the establishment of remote-control standards and training will follow a similar trajectory as the Electronic Chart Display and Information System (ECDIS) standards for training. As ECDIS technology became more widely adopted, it became clear that crew training was critical to its effective use. IMO recognized this and in 1995 issued a resolution recommending that training in the use of ECDIS be included in STCW. Following the IMO's recommendation, various maritime authorities began to develop and implement standards for ECDIS training. Over time, the standards for ECDIS training have become more standardized, with the IMO issuing its first model course on ECDIS training in 2012. This model course provides guidance on the knowledge, skills, and competencies required to use ECDIS effectively and safely.

In the same manner, initially, remote control will be introduced on a limited number of vessels, gradually becoming standardized and widespread. Following this, it may be expected that an international standard will be established for remote control operators in general. Given that multiple organizations worldwide are involved in developing the technology, it is anticipated that operators will need to undergo a type-specific course for the intended remote-control center. This will enable them to possess a more comprehensive understanding of the equipment, systems, and processes they will encounter in their respective roles and ensure a greater degree of proficiency and competence in remote vessel operations.

The implementation of remote-control operation will face challenges despite its contribution to safe navigation. Officers who attend remote-control operation training and complete familiarization may still not be confident or competent when it comes to critical safety settings. Although there is ongoing work to ensure the effective use of remote-control operation, it is important to understand that specific and periodic training is necessary, as digitalization at sea is expanding into all aspects of seafarers' tasks.

Since the effectiveness of a system is dependent on its users, training should extend beyond simply checking off the equipment manufacturers' manual and the possible future IMO-mandated training. However, the diversity and fragmentation of digital system train-

ing programs may result in the absence of the best practice benchmark for ship remote-control operators to aspire to. Additionally, there is a lack of knowledge sharing between vessel remote-control developers and training organizations on effective real-life approaches and practical challenges.

Future implementation in maritime education

In light of the rapid expansion of digitalization and remote-control technologies in the maritime industry, it is imperative that maritime education and training (MET) facilities remain vigilant and attentive to the evolving landscape. As such, organizations such as DNV and platforms such as PLATINA3 have been at the forefront of developing standards and guidelines to ensure the safe and effective use of remote-control technologies. Nonetheless, it is the responsibility of MET institutions to remain up to date with these advancements and incorporate them into their curricula accordingly. The future of the maritime industry is inching towards the use of remote-control centers, which will necessitate the deployment of trained operators. In response, MET facilities must adapt their educational programs to encompass the technical knowledge and practical skills required of such operators. To achieve this, these necessary requirements must be satisfied: a comprehensive understanding of the remote-control technologies in use, a sound grasp of the operational procedures involved, and a thorough awareness of the safety implications and risks associated with the use of these technologies [16]. In order for MET to achieve their ultimate objective of adequately preparing and training future operators for remote control vessels, there are three prerequisites that must be met.

In order to effectively prepare future remote control vessel operators, the first and foremost prerequisite is the provision of highly detailed, comprehensive, and globally recognized standards for training, which will serve as the foundation upon which institutions can establish their training programs. It is imperative that these standards are developed to the highest degree of quality and accuracy in order to ensure that the training provided meets the industry's exacting requirements. Furthermore, in order to guarantee the quality of training offered, a robust certification framework must also be established to ensure that only those institutions which meet the requisite standards are authorized to provide the training. Given the highly specialized nature of the training and the complex equipment involved, not every institution will possess the necessary resources to offer training of a sufficiently high caliber. Therefore, it is essential that a comprehensive and rigorous certification system is established to safeguard the quality and efficacy of the training provided.

In order to successfully prepare and train future operators, the second prerequisite that MET facilities must fulfill is to provide access to specialized remote-control simulators that are specifically designed for training purposes. Existing simulators are generally designed to accommodate multiple users, making them unsuitable for operator training, as they require the operation of different instruments and controls by differ-

ent individuals simultaneously. This design is not compatible with the concept of a single operator monitoring and controlling all aspects of navigation, with all controls within easy reach. As a result, MET facilities will have to invest in new simulation stations that are specifically designed for remote-control operation training, which will require not only new hardware but also new software. Given the expected demand for remote-control training, it is likely that major simulator software brands are already developing similar software for remote-control stations or are planning to do so in the near future.

The third and final prerequisite pertains to the trainers responsible for imparting the necessary skills to future remote-control operators. A significant question that arises is, what credentials are required for a trainer to deliver adequate training? Would practical experience as a remote-control operator or a seafarer, or both, be necessary? Furthermore, what specific competencies should trainers be capable of imparting to trainees to ensure their proficiency in operating remote-control vessels? These are critical issues that, despite their relevance, will likely be addressed last in the process of preparing MET facilities for providing adequate training for remote-control operators.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the advancement of automation technology requires the establishment of competency standards for operators who will operate and supervise remote control systems. DNV has made substantial progress in this area and has introduced the first competence standard for operators of ship remote control centers along with a recommended practice for a certification scheme. The inland water transport sector also needs new competencies for nautical inland shipping personnel involved in remote operations. The current state of development of standards for remote control operators is still in its embryonic stage, and the maritime and inland waterway transport industries are waiting for remote control vessels to become more actively involved in global trade before seriously contemplating the necessity for establishing standards and guidelines in this field. The implementation of remote-control operation will face challenges despite its contribution to safe navigation. Therefore, it is important to understand that specific and periodic training is necessary, as digitalization at sea is expanding into all aspects of seafarers' tasks.

Notes

1. DNV. Supporting remote control operations in shipping: DNV publishes a pioneering new competence standard and recommended practice. 2021. Available online: <https://www.dnv.com/news/supporting-remote-control-operations-in-shipping-dnv-publishes-pioneering-new-competence-standard-and-recommended-practice-213200>

2. ICS. Shipping Facts. [Online]. Available at <https://www.ics-shipping.org/explaining/shipping-facts/>

3. IMO. Autonomous Shipping. 2018. [Online]. Available at: <https://www.imo.org/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/Pages/Autonomous-shipping.aspx>

4. IMO. Circular Letter No. 4204/Add. 6. 2020. [Online]. Available at: <https://wwwcdn.imo.org/localresources/en/MediaCentre/HotTopics/Documents/Circular%20Letter%20No.4204Add.6%20%20Coronavirus%20Covid-19%20Preliminary%20List%20Of%20Recommendations.pdf>

5. IMO. Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) Proposal for a Regulatory Scoping Exercise. IMO: London, UK, 2017.

6. IMO. MSC.1/Circ.1598. 2019. [Online]. Available at <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/HumanElement/Pages/Fatigue.aspx>.

7. IMO. Regulatory Scoping Exercise for the Use of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS); MSC 99/WP.9; IMO: London, UK, 2018.

8. Kongsberg. Autonomous Shipping. 2020. Available online: <https://www.kongsberg.com/maritime/support/themes/autonomous-shipping/>.

9. Lloyd's Register. LR Code for Unmanned Marine Systems; Lloyd's Register: London, UK, 2017.

10. Maritime Executive. Construction of Yara Birkeland Paused. Available online: <https://www.maritimeexecutive.com/article/construction-of-yara-birkeland-paused>.

11. Maritime UK. Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) UK Industry Conduct Principles and Code of Practice; Maritime UK: Southampton, UK, 2019.

12. Rolls-Royce. Rolls-Royce and Finferries Demonstrate World's First Fully Autonomous Ferry. [Online] Available: <https://www.rolls-royce.com/media/press-releases/2018/03-12-2018-rr-and-finferries-demonstrate-worlds-first-fully-autonomous-ferry.aspx>

13. Report on competences needed to operate on board systems allowing for automation of inland navigation vessels D3.3. [Online] Available online: <https://platina3.eu/download/competences-for-on-board-systems-allowing-for-automation/>

14. NYK. NYK Conducts World's First Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships Trial. 2019. Available online: https://www.nyk.com/english/news/2019/20190930_01.html.

15. NYK. NYK to Participate in Crewless Maritime Autonomous Surface Ship Trial Project. Available online: https://www.nyk.com/english/news/2020/20200615_01.html

References

1. AHVENJARVI, S., 2016. The Human Element and Autonomous Ships. *TransNav International Journal of Maritime Navigation and Safety of Sea Transportation* [Online], vol. 10 (3), September, pp. 453-458. [viewed 25 April 2023]. DOI: 10.12716/1001.10.03.18.

2. CICEK, K., AKYUZ, E., CELIK, M. 2019. Future Skills Requirements Analysis in Maritime Industry. *Procedia Computer Science* [Online], vol. 158, pp. 270-274. ISSN 1877-0509. [viewed 13 April 2023]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.051>.

3. CHHABRA, Y. 2018. *A Mariner's Guide to Navigational Watches: Principles and Best Practices*. Mumbai.

4. CORADDU, A.; ONETO, L.; NAVAS DE MAYA, B.; KURT, R., 2020. Determining the Most Influential Human Factors in Maritime Accidents: A Data-Driven Approach. *OCEAN ENGINEERING*, vol. 211, pp. 107588.
5. EMAD, G.R.; GHOSH, S. Identifying essential skills and competencies towards building a training framework for future operators of autonomous ships: a qualitative study. *WMU Journal of Maritime Affairs* [Online]. Advance online publication. [viewed 14 April 2023]. DOI: 10.1007/s13437-023-00310-9.
6. EMAD, G.R.; KHABIR, M.; SHAHBAKHS, M. 2020. Shipping 4.0 and Training Seafarers for the Future Autonomous and Unmanned Ships. 21st Marine Industries Conference (MIC2019) [Online]
7. GRAY, D. 1967. Automation in Ships. In BONWICK, G. (Ed.), *Automation on Shipboard*, pp. 19-34. New York, NY, USA: MacMillan and Company.
8. HANNAFORD, E. & HASSEL, E.V. 2021. Risks and Benefits of Crew Reduction and/or Removal with Increased Automation for the Ship Operator: A Licensed Deck Officer's Perspective. *Applied Sciences* [Online], vol. 11, pp. 3569. [viewed 25 April 2023]. DOI: 10.3390/app11083569.
9. HOGG, T. & GHOSH, S. 2016. Autonomous Merchant Vessels: Examination of Factors That Impact the Effective Implementation of Unmanned Ships. *Australian Journal of Maritime & Ocean Affairs*, vol. 8, pp. 206-222.
10. HYNNEKLEIV, A., LUTZHOF, M., & EARTHY, J.V. 2020. Towards an ecosystem of skills in the future maritime industry. *Human Factors*, February.
11. KARI, R. & STEINERT, M. 2021. Human Factor Issues in Remote Ship Operations: Lessons Learned by Studying Different Domains. *J. Mar. Sci. Eng.* [Online], vol. 9 (4), pp. 385. [viewed 25 April 2023]. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse9040385>.
12. KENNARD, A.; ZHANG, P.; RAJAGOPAL, S., 2022. Technology and training: How will deck officers transition to operating autonomous and remote-controlled vessels? *Marine Policy* [Online], vol. 146, pp. 105326. ISSN 0308-597X. [viewed 13 April 2023]. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105326.
13. NAVA, G. & FERNANDA, P.M. 2019. Legal Challenges of Liability in Collisions Arising from the Development of Autonomous and Unmanned Shipping—International and Norwegian Perspective. Master's Thesis, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway.
14. RAMOS, M.A.; UTNE, I.; MOSLEH, A. 2018. On factors affecting autonomous ships operators' performance in a Shore Control Center. In *Proceedings of the 14th Probabilistic Safety Assessment and Management*, Los Angeles, CA, USA, 16–21 September 2018.
15. RAMOS, M. A.; UTNE, I. B.; MOSLEH, A., 2019. Collision avoidance on maritime autonomous surface ships: Operators' tasks and human failure events. *Safety Science*, vol. 116, pp. 33-44.
16. RODSETH, O.J.; BURMEISTER, H.-C. 2015. Risk Assessment for an Unmanned Merchant Ship. *TransNav Int. J. Mar. Navig. Saf. Sea Transp.* [Online], vol. 9, (3), pp. 357–364 [viewed 25 April 2023]. DOI: 10.12716/1001.09.03.08
17. TVETE, H. 2015. ReVolt: The Unmanned, Zero Emission, Short Sea Ship of the Future [Online]. DNV GL Strategic Research & Innovation: Hovik, Norway.
18. YOSHIDA, M., SHIMIZU, E., SUGOMORI, M. & UMEDA, A. 2020. Regulatory Requirements on the Competence of Remote Operators in Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships: Situation Awareness, Ship Sense, and Goal-Based Gap Analysis. *Applied Sciences* [Online], vol. 10, (23), pp. 8751. [viewed 25 April 2023]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10238751>